

RIGHTS AND LEGAL INTERESTS OF A WITNESS

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Abstract: In this article, the procedural status of a witness, who is an important participant in criminal proceedings in the administration of justice, as well as some problems in the application of legal norms to ensure the safety of witnesses in order to ensure the reliability of their testimony, which is an important guarantee of making a lawful, fair, and reasonable decision in establishing the truth in the case, are analyzed.

Keywords: witness, legal status of a witness, rights and interests of a person, criminal procedure, safety of participants in the process, security measures.

According to procedural rules, absolute confidentiality of personal data about a witness is allowed by a court decision. At the same time, measures to ensure the absolute confidentiality of personal data relating to the witness are limited not only to the confidentiality of personal data, but also allow testimony to be carried out on the screen by changing the appearance and voice of the witness. However, in practice, such procedural measures are most often applied in cases involving witnesses who have suddenly witnessed a crime, as well as members of an organized criminal group. If the defendant (accused person) is well acquainted with the witness, then there is no need to conceal the witness's identity. Because the defendant (the accused) can easily identify the identity of the anonymous witness participating under the pseudonym, at least from the content of the information in the testimony¹.

One of the effective procedural measures providing for the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of a witness is the concept of absolute confidentiality of personal data².

As I. A. Surovenko and O. A. Chabukiani rightly pointed out in this matter, in practice there are cases when a person with significant information about a criminal case is known not only to law enforcement officers but also to criminals about their identity and the possibility of questioning this person in connection with the criminal case. In this case, it is inappropriate to confidentialize

¹ Criminal Justice. An introduction to the Criminal Justice System in England and Wales. London, 1995.

² Criminal Justice. An introduction to the Criminal Justice System in England and Wales. London, 1995;

Braithwaite J., Mugford S. Conditions of Successful Reintegration Ceremonies: Dealing with Juvenile Offenders//British Journal of Criminology. 1994. № 34. P 78.

information about a person who has significant information about the criminal case. Instead, it is necessary to take measures to ensure the safety of this person³.

According to the rules established in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Federal Republic of Germany, information relating to a witness is strictly confidential by the court at the request of the investigator or prosecutor. In this case, a police or law enforcement officer may testify about the information the witness has on the case. A police officer or law enforcement officer giving testimony on behalf of a witness is not entitled to disclose information about the witness's identity when testifying about the information held by the witness and to question the authenticity of the information provided by the witness.

According to this procedure, the defense may submit questions to the witness in writing through a police officer, and the witness, in turn, may submit answers to the questions to the court in writing through a police officer or law enforcement officer giving testimony on their behalf⁴.

The participation of a confidential witness in criminal proceedings is also regulated by the laws of Japan in the field of criminal proceedings. In particular, according to the amendments made to the Criminal Procedure Code of Japan in 2016, in criminal cases conducted by the prosecutor's office and the National Police Agency, the testimony of a suspect, accused, as well as a witness, part of it, or the entire interrogation process must be recorded on video and submitted to the court (judge). However, according to the Criminal Procedure Code of the country, the testimony of a suspect, accused, as well as a witness, must be recorded on video and submitted to the court in the following cases: a) in criminal cases in which an extraordinary measure of punishment may be applied; b) in criminal cases in which a punishment in the form of imprisonment for a term exceeding one year may be applied for a criminal act that led to the death of a victim; c) in criminal cases under the jurisdiction of the prosecutor's office⁵.

³ *Суровенко И. А., Чабукиани О. А.* Проблемные аспекты обеспечения безопасности свидетеля, участвующего в следственных действиях под псевдонимом // Научный диалог. 2013/ Выпуск № 7 (19): Экономика. Право. Политология. –С.142-143. *Фирсов С. Н., Домнина Е. В.* Особенности проведения допроса свидетеля в условиях исключаяющих его визуальное наблюдение / Пробелы в российском законодательстве. Юридический журнал. 2018, №7. –С.97-99. *Дмитриева А. А.* Новые правила оглашения показаний судом как усиление гарантий процессуальной безопасности участников уголовного процесса // Вестник Южно-Уральского государственного университета. Серия: Право. 2016. № 2. С. 76–79.

⁴ Федеративная Республика Германия. Уголовно-процессуальный кодекс. –М.: Издательская фирма "Монускрипт", 1994.

⁵ *Волосова Н. Ю./Volosova N. U.* Matters of Russian and International Law. 2018, Vol. 8, Is. 8A Реформа уголовного судопроизводства Японии–С.183-186.

Thus, based on the analysis of the procedural norms in force in foreign countries regulating the participation of a confidential or pseudonymous witness in criminal proceedings, the following conclusions can be drawn: 1) a confidential witness is a specific participant in criminal proceedings, which is manifested in the confidentiality of the personal data of a witness who has significant information about the criminal case, and in some cases, in the restriction of the witness's face-to-face meeting with other participants in the criminal proceedings; 2) the issue of protecting the rights and legitimate interests of a confidential witness consists of both procedural and general legal measures; 3) several procedural and legal conditions under which the confidentiality of information about the identity of a participant in a criminal case, possessing certain information, is important. These are: a) the degree of social danger of the crime; b) the significance of the information available to the witness in solving the crime; c) the similarity of the circumstances in the witness's testimony to the crime; 4) the confidentiality of personal information relating to the witness and information relating to his relatives is an important procedural tool; 5) procedural rules for the legalization of testimony of a confidential witness in court proceedings have been developed, in which technical and technological means of modern technologies occupy an important place (Japan, USA, France, etc.); 6) in some countries (Germany, Austria, etc.), a third party (often an operative-investigative officer, a police officer) may be involved in delivering the testimony of a confidential witness to the court and other participants. In this case, the third party participates not as a witness, but as a person who transmits information about the circumstances of the criminal case that the confidential witness possesses; 7) the trust of the court and other participants in the testimony of a confidential witness, as well as the assessment of the information contained in them, exists as an important procedural and legal problem. Scientists and specialists often classify the indirect, covert testimony of a confidential witness as highly unreliable evidence and emphasize that such testimony should be evaluated based on all evidence gathered in the criminal case (for example, in German law and theory).

Based on the above analysis, the introduction into the Criminal Procedure Code of rules regulating relations related to the participation of a confidential or pseudonymous witness in criminal proceedings is an important issue for the legislation of our country. Its relevance increases if we take into account that the Criminal Procedure Code provides for the participation of a "witness with a pseudonym," and there are no provisions regulating his status, rights, and

legitimate interests. Based on these considerations, it is necessary to make appropriate amendments and additions to the Criminal Procedure Code. In our view, it is advisable to place the proposed regulatory amendments and additions in this area in accordance with the structure of the stages of criminal proceedings. This work should begin, first of all, with the "pre-trial investigation" stage, which constitutes the "pre-trial stage" of the criminal process. Because the goals and objectives of the pre-investigation check stage "imply a system of procedural actions of responsible state bodies and officials with appropriate powers, aimed at issuing a lawful and justified decision by collecting, examining, and evaluating evidence on applications, reports, and other information related to a crime"⁶.

Based on the indicated grounds, it is necessary to develop rules regulating the relationship to ensure the confidentiality of the personal data of the informer, depending on the degree of public danger of the crime, the significance of the report, and the prospects for the person's participation in criminal proceedings (for example, a witness, victim, participant in the crime), if their identity is known to law enforcement agencies⁷. On this basis, it is advisable to supplement Article 328 of the Criminal Procedure Code with a second part⁸.

In addition, in order to form a mechanism for the proper functioning of proposals for making appropriate amendments to the above-mentioned procedural norms, it is necessary to take measures to ensure the safety of persons who have significant information about the circumstances of the crime, if there are reasonable suspicions about the existence of a serious threat to their safety or the possibility of such a threat arising in the future, in the procedural norms that determine the procedure for considering applications, reports, and other information about crimes. Because the amendments and additions to the procedural norm, firstly, allow for the formation of a system for ensuring the safety of a person who has significant information about a crime; secondly, such an approach will promptly ensure the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of a person who has significant information about a crime.

Therefore, it is necessary to supplement Article 329 of the Criminal Procedure Code with parts four and five, respectively⁹.

⁶ Ботаев М. Дж. Терговга қадар текширув институтини такомиллаштириш: Юридик фанлар бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси Автореферати. -Т., Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ички ишлар вазирлиги Академияси. 2020. –Б.13.

⁷ Диссертациянинг 1-иловасига қаранг

⁸ Диссертациянинг 1-иловасига қаранг

⁹ Диссертациянинг 1-иловасига қаранг

The proposed amendment to Article 329 of the Criminal Procedure Code requires amendments and additions to Article 330 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to strengthen the regulatory framework for the implementation of procedural actions provided for in the proposed amendment. In particular, such an addition should serve as a procedural and legal basis only in exceptional circumstances, i.e., if there is a need to ensure the safety of the person who reported the crime¹⁰.

Therefore, it is necessary to supplement Article 330 of the Criminal Procedure Code, which regulates the rules regarding decisions made as a result of the consideration of criminal information, with a second part, ensuring the safety of persons who reported the commission of a crime.

The confidentiality of the personal data of the person who reported the commission of the crime must begin with the decision to initiate criminal proceedings, if the criminal case is initiated directly on the basis of the person's report. Therefore, in the descriptive part of the decision to initiate a criminal case due to a person's report, instead of the personal data of the person who reported the crime, it is advisable to use the pseudonym provided for in Article 380 of the Criminal Procedure Code and Article 114¹ to be added to it. There are several reasons for this, including, firstly, if the personal data of the person who reported the crime (for example: first name, patronymic and surname, place of residence, etc.) are indicated in the decision, then the subsequent confidentiality of their personal data becomes insignificant; secondly, the central issue in this problem is ensuring the safety of the person who reported the crime; thirdly, it creates a specific direction of proving activity in criminal proceedings, a special form of evidence. Because the central issue of criminal proceedings is proving the guilt of the defendant, the testimony of a person whose personal data is confidential (later a witness in the case) can serve as important evidence. After all, the task of proof is to convince the prosecution, primarily the judge (court, judge), of the validity of their point of view.

Because an important aspect of this issue is convincing the decision-maker. The judge, in accordance with Article 95 of the Criminal Procedure Code, assesses the testimony of a witness with a pseudonym in the totality of other evidence collected in the case.

Undoubtedly, the analyzed issue may create certain procedural and legal problems. For example, defense in criminal proceedings is related to convincing the party that a witness with a pseudonym is not a product of the abuse of official

¹⁰ Диссертациянинг 1-иловасига қаранг

duties of the persons conducting the criminal case, but is indeed reliable evidence. If the defendant's fate is decided solely on the basis of the testimony of a "classified" witness, this may be the main problem. But there is nothing wrong with the fact that the evidence collected in the case coincides with the testimony of a witness with a pseudonym. Also, the main thing here is not who the person with the pseudonym is, but the content of the circumstances stated in his message (later in his testimony).

The main issue of procedural measures related to ensuring the safety of a witness with significant information is related to his procedural status and the procedure for ensuring the rights and freedoms of the witness. Because a witness with a pseudonym participating in criminal procedural legal relations must have a clear understanding of the scope of rights and legitimate interests. In our opinion, when creating this norm, it is necessary to pay attention to four important aspects. First, the concept of the status of a witness with a pseudonym; second, the rights and freedoms granted to a witness with a pseudonym; third, the obligations of a witness with a pseudonym; fourth, the form and limits of ensuring the safety of a witness with a pseudonym.

The aforementioned legal norms, which determine the procedural status of a person who has information about a committed crime, also require the establishment of rules for interrogating a witness with a pseudonym. After all, the content of measures to ensure the safety of a person who has significant information about the circumstances of the criminal case is precisely to ensure the confidentiality of information about his personality from other persons participating in the criminal case. Therefore, the formation of rules related to the confidentiality of information about the identity of a witness with a pseudonym in investigative actions conducted with his participation reflects an important aspect of this procedural institution.

In our opinion, when solving this problem, it is necessary to rely on two criteria. The first is to ensure the person's own safety (fully or partially) at all stages of the interrogation process; the second is to ensure the full or partial confidentiality of personal data during the interrogation of a witness with a pseudonym, i.e., a form of security measures taken against a person.

Summarizing the above considerations, it should be noted that the institution of protecting the safety of a witness with a pseudonym by legal means and methods serves as a guarantee of ensuring the safety of witnesses at the judicial and pre-trial stages, as well as a specific element of the administration of justice. The procedural norms adopted in the USA in the seventies of the last century,

providing for the safety of witnesses, are still one of the important measures for the administration of justice in some especially serious criminal cases. In our view, this procedural institution will become one of the means ensuring the fulfillment by witnesses of their social duties.

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